

**The Future for Moscow:
An Economic Risk Profile of the Russian Federation**

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Modern international politics can be characterized by a global economy and every country's role within world markets. Adversaries fight trade wars and multinational corporations are increasingly larger actors in international relations and economics. As of 2022 and 2023, relations between Western nations, including the US or the UK, and the two Eastern powers, Russia and China have been the most tenuous in the past couple of decades since the collapse of the Soviet Union. With the decision to invade Ukraine by the Russian president, Vladimir Putin, in early 2022, international condemnation of such a breach of sovereignty has resulted in international action. The country has largely been cut off from Western markets in ways that hurt its key exports and necessities. With China watching the invasion as a comparable situation to their desire for Taiwan in the South China Sea, questions about Russian economic health arise. Thus the guiding question for this paper is: what is the current profile of Russian economics, and how can the Nation's current global position be understood?

Russian Industry

Even during the Soviet Union, Russia has always been heavily reliant on its abundance of natural resources. An industrial profile of the nation by Encyclopedia Britannica outlines the variety and size of each main industry in the Russian Federation. The country has vast amounts of raw minerals and energy sources which fund a massive coal, oil, and natural gas industry that exports much of the world's supply. One-fifth of all oil is extracted in Russia and over one-fourth of the global natural gas supply is due to Russian exports. The overwhelming amount of natural gas is extracted from underground fields in western Siberia, although other sites produce large amounts as well: all in the northern half of the country. In terms of coal, due to the absence of current needs and the distance, there are enormous untapped coal reserve sites in eastern Siberia at the Tunguska and Lena basins which exist as a major asset for the Russian economy. While three-fourths of Russian electricity comes from thermal power plants fueled with oil and gas, Russian energy has become an

increasingly diversified industry with hundreds of power plants throughout the country, the majority being hydroelectric alongside 38 nuclear facilities.

Another large part of the Russian economic system is the manufacturing industry which includes machinery, being the bulk of the industry, chemicals, and textiles. The chemical sector utilizes the great amounts of raw minerals within the country including salt deposits and timber to produce a variety of products such as synthetic rubber. Textiles being the other relatively small portion of this industry has a concentration in European Russia around Moscow. Machinery though is the industry's largest sector, not only propping up the sector but being the largest portion of the Russian economy. All of the country's machinery needs are generally fulfilled without heavy imports and Russia exports tens of billions of dollars in machinery to mainly Kazakhstan, Belarus, China, and India.

Figure 1

Bar graph showing largest wheat exporters

Note. The graph shows a chart of the world's ten largest wheat exporters in 2020 in millions of tons. The figure was sourced from *The World's Largest Wheat Exporters* [Infographic]. (2022, March 18). World Economic Forum. which gathered its data from the Food and Agriculture Organization, and Reuters.

The other of the big three industries in Russia is a combination of agriculture, forestry, and fishing. The unfit climate of the majority of the nation leaves small portions dedicated to agriculture and farming which takes about an eighth of the labor force. The emphasis of the sector is on wheat and grain, for which it is the world's largest exporter.

Figure 2

Russian Agricultural Output

Note. The graph shows two piecewise linear functions which represent the growth in agricultural output of Russia against the world. The figure was sourced from “*Agricultural output, 1961 to 2019* [Chart]. (2022, October 7). *Our World in Data*. which gathered its data from the United State Department of Agriculture Economic Research Service.

Also, it is an industry backed by the previously mentioned machinery industry which manufactures agriculture equipment on a large scale. Although the agriculture sector is big for the nation, it has been heavily outpaced historically and has become increasingly irrelevant on a global scale as shown in Figure 2. The forestry sector is less important and has grown at a much slower

rate than other parts of the Russian economy. However, Russia has one-fifth of the world's total forests which accumulate geographically to almost the size of the continental United States. Therefore, timber is a large and available asset for the economy. Finally, fishing is the third part of the labor-based resource harvesting section of the economy and is a big player for Russia overall. The industry has access to both the Pacific and Atlantic oceans and maintains numerous fleets of fishing vessels that make Russia the supplier of one-third of the world's canned fish and one-fourth of the world's fresh and frozen fish (*Economy of Russia*, 2023).

Russian Banking

With around 350 banks and around 240 of them maintaining over a billion in equity, the Russian banking system is sizable. The system has largely been stuck in the past in terms of technology. In 2012, 76% of transactions were still made with cash. However, the nation has made efforts to modernize and thus that number has dropped dramatically in recent years (Maunder, 2023). The Russian Central Bank has worked hard to combat very unstable inflation over the past 20 years or so. The inflation rate sits at 11% as of February 2023, and the bank has a target rate of 4%.

Figure 3

Trends in Russian inflation

Note. The graph shows the Russian inflation rate during the 2006-2020 time period, and a bar chart measuring the annual change in the inflation rate. The figure was sourced from *Russia Inflation Rate 1993-2023* [Chart]. (n.d.). macro-trends, which gathered its data from the World Bank.

Figure 4

Trends in Russian interest rates

Note. The graph shows the benchmark interest rate of the Bank of Russia from the time period of 2020-2023. The figure was sourced from The New York Times. (2022, December 16). *Bank of Russia's benchmark interest rate* [Chart]. The New York Times. .which gathered its data from the Bank of Russia.

To achieve this 4% target, the Russian central bank has played with its benchmark interest rate a lot in the past couple of years since the war in Ukraine started. Unable to combat inflation during an international boycotting of their systems, the country has made inflation a secondary concern. The inflation rate reached a staggering 20.37% in April of 2022 after Putin made the decision to send troops across the Ukrainian border. However, the central bank acted fast raising interest rates as high as 20%. Now forcing that number down to 7.5% in order to revitalize an increasingly stand-still economy. Now the Bank of Russia is caught between the choices of fully

isolationist economic revamping, or sustaining a goal of international trade and participation, in which case, their inflation rate becomes their downfall.

The six largest banks in the nation are SberBank, VTB, Gazprombank, VTB24, Bank Otkritie Financial Corporation, and the Bank of Moscow with SberBank being state-owned. SberBank, VTB, and Gazprom are among the largest corporations in the world. SberBank reported massive losses in 2022 with a net profit of 270 billion rubles, about 3.56 billion USD, which was a 78.3% decrease from the year before. The bank attributed it to the international sanctions against them and other major Russian corporations. The timeline went, Russian troops crossed the Ukrainian border in February, SberBank chose to withdraw from the European market in March, and in May SberBank was cut off from the SWIFT global payment financial system (*Russia's Biggest Bank Announces Huge 2022 Fall in Profits, 2023*). Despite this, SberBank investment funds available to Russian investors are still heavily invested in Western equities, a majority being US blue chips. For example, the SberBank Global Internet Fund is invested primarily in US tech stocks like Microsoft, Apple, and Meta, still being in the top four holdings right behind a one-off Chinese Internet ETF. Despite over 75% of this portfolio being in US tech stocks greatly hurt by a US recession, the P/E ratio of the fund sits at about 23%. This makes it attractive, even in the US, as a safer investment currently, let alone the inflationary situation in Russia (*Sberbank Global Internet (0P0000WDGZ), 2023*).

The next largest Bank is VTB which has acquired 15 other banks since 2002 including 2 of the Russian top six, Bank of Moscow and VTB24. Other notable acquisitions include Eurobank in France and Ost-West Handelsbank Germany, a former soviet controlled bank. The acquired institutions span Europe and almost all are under the VTB moniker such as Eurobank now known as VTB France. While not completely owned by the Russian state, over 92% is split among three Russian agencies (Reuters Staff, 2022).

Overall, the Russian banking system has been hit hard and tough decisions have been made. Russia appears to have defaulted on its international debt for the first time in over a century due to Western sanctions, making it impossible for the country to pay its overseas creditors. After Russia invaded Ukraine in February, the United States and Europe froze the country's access to foreign currency assets held overseas, putting Russia on default watch. Russia transferred rubles through unsanctioned banks to pay its debts, and the Kremlin rejects the default label as artificially made by Western sanctions. The impact is expected to be minimal immediately, but long-term questions remain regarding Russia's standing with friendly countries, its ability to borrow on the international market, and the potential depletion of its coffers due to sanctions (Selyukh, 2023).

Conclusions could and have been made on the persistence of nationalization and monopolization within the Russian banking industry. This results in the slowing of economic progress for which the financial sector is the main cause in the twenty-first century (Bitkina & Korenkova, 2018). However, the spread of holdings and the size of its top institutions may be enough to keep it relevant and able to function on an internal level.

Role of Russia in International Economic Development

The World Bank has discussed Russia's efforts to increase its development cooperation agenda in line with the OECD-DAC principles of ownership, alignment, transparency, accountability, and monitoring to achieve the Millennium Development Goals of the United Nations. Since adopting its national aid strategy in 2007, Russia has taken significant steps to scale up its Official Development Assistance (ODA) and participated in international fora such as APEC, G20, and BRICS. The priority areas of Russia's international development assistance at both regional and global levels include improving governance systems and trade and investment conditions, building industrial and innovation capacities, boosting economic activity, establishing and strengthening national systems to combat organized crime and terrorism, supporting post-conflict peacebuilding, and implementing social and economic projects in recipient countries.

Russia's ODA increased from about \$100 million in 2004 to \$1,188 million in 2017, with a focus on health, food security, agriculture, human development, education, and institutional capacity building. Russia has also supported the International Development Association (IDA) and various multilateral agencies, including trust funds administered by the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD). The article concludes by stating that the World Bank Group's future cooperation with Russia will focus on engaging Russia as a provider of global public goods (*Russia and the World Bank: International Development Assistance*, 2023).

Figure 5

Note. The graph shows the amount, in millions of USD of Russian official development assistance. The figure was sourced from *Russian Official Development Assistance, mln. USD* [Map]. (2023). The World Bank, which gathered its data from the World Bank.

Overall, Russia has taken more and more action over the past few decades in supporting international development initiatives. As of 2015, the nation was ranked seventh for contribution and thus voting power for two of the four World Bank bodies and eleventh for another. However, when thinking about the nation's role in furthering development, they only ranked out of the top twenty for the International Development Association; the time of this ranking, 2015, being a national high for development assistance contribution (*International Bank for Reconstruction and*

Development Subscriptions and Voting Power of Member Countries, 2015; International Finance Corporation Subscriptions and Voting Power of Member Countries, 2015; International Development Association Voting Power of Member Countries, 2015; Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency Subscriptions and Voting Power of Member Countries, 2015).

Global Trade and Influence

Russia's intervention in Syria and Libya in 2015 marked its return as a major actor in the Mediterranean. The country has been using all elements of statecraft, including diplomatic, ideological, military, and economic instruments, to advance its interests in this region, which is a vital shipping and transit corridor. However, a closer look at Russia's economic tool kit in this region suggests that concerns about Russian economic capabilities are likely overstated. Russia's most important economic tools in the Mediterranean are its energy resources, arms exports, and ability to launder money through corrupt networks. These tools have complemented Russia's diplomatic and military activities, particularly in areas where economic systems and rule of law have been weaker. Not only have sanctions dampened if not cut off their use in the region, but these tools have also proved of limited utility elsewhere, as they have not been backed by the traditional instruments of economic statecraft: trade in non-energy goods and services, foreign direct investment, and development assistance (Pritchett, 2021).

Based on economic data available, Russia's bilateral trade with individual Mediterranean countries is low, its investment levels in most Mediterranean countries are insubstantial, and it is not giving large quantities of development assistance to the poorer countries along the Mediterranean's eastern and southern rims. Without these traditional economic ties, Russia's economic diplomacy in the region is highly based on symbolism, and the relationships lack sustainability over the long term, which undercuts its geopolitical ambitions in the Mediterranean (Pritchett, 2021).

The United States and the European Union (EU) have generally excelled in building economic ties in the post-World War II era and continue to be the dominant economic powers in the

Mediterranean. Continuing this leadership in the economy will likely ensure that Russian influence in the Mediterranean remains a manageable, if persistent, problem for the West (Pritchett, 2021). In trying to combat this issue along with the present international condemnation of the Ukraine War, the West took measures to slow the exportation of oil from Russia. In December 2022, these measures took effect to limit Russian oil profits which may mean a lower global supply of crude oil in exchange for hurting the Russian economy. This furthers the sanctions already in place which have previously had a lower-than-intended effect on Russian economics. However, these measures are more direct and include a ban on oil by the European Union and a price cap of \$60 per barrel by the Western democracies in terms of Russian exports to other sovereign nations that value democratic ties. However, the effects may be lower than expected seeing as Russia has been able to redirect the majority of its European exports to Asian countries such as China and India. Furthermore, these new routes are at steep discounts for the importers thus lowering the effect of the price cap. Chris Weafer, CEO of consultancy Macro-Advisory, stated that the Kremlin and its greater economy have enough funds to maintain its operations in Ukraine and manage the governmental obligations of the Russian state at the same time. The Western hope is thus that these new buyers are unable or unwilling to continue purchasing at high enough volumes to maintain this.

The fear is that this price cap along with other measures will cause a shortage and widen growing inflation rates around the world. The solution would be that these Western nations would possibly have to back down. However, the looming threat of rising energy costs is very real when sanctioning the world's second-largest producer. Lauri Myllyvirta, a lead analyst at the Centre for Research on Energy and Clean Air, stated that the effective strategy would be to push the cap down even more "quickly and progressively." But they also stated that the \$60 price cap is a record step towards shutting down Russia's egregious military actions. The stubborn and unwilling stance however was held by Dmitry Peskov when he answered a question by stating that Russia has the ability to maintain its invasion.

In the past, Russian oil has been the main supplier for Europe which has struggled quickly to find replacement suppliers. Thus, the reasoning behind previous sanctions which were more related to Russian financial institutions. However, hitting Moscow's oil machine is incredibly more effective. In response to the price cap Russia made threats to nations who agreed to it; that they would be cut off from Russian oil. John Kirby, National Security Council spokesman for the Biden administration, stated that Russian threats would not affect oil prices in the long term, instead the cap will allow the nations where Russia has rerouted their oil to negotiate for even larger discounts in exchange for maintaining their purchasing relationship. It is also important to understand the price cap's grace period, which doesn't affect shipments currently in transit. Overall, world leaders have all reacted to the price cap in different ways. Examples of negative reactions include the French finance minister being unimpressed and Ukraine rightfully calling for an even lower price cap (Associated Press, 2022).

Before the War in Ukraine, the Russian economy benefited from foreign interaction. The nation's foreign assets outweighed its foreign debt by a little under half a trillion dollars. These assets accounted for 7% of Russian GDP (Milesi-Ferretti, 2022).

Figure 6

Horizontal bar graph showing Russian foreign assets and liabilities

Note. From "Russia's external position: Does financial autarky protect against sanctions?" by G.M. Milesi-Ferretti.

Foreign policy decisions maintained this through a pattern of proportional investment to financing over the past decade. Financial flows peaked in 2013, late 2014, and 2021. In 2013, the nation's financial sector was strong and they enacted their largest year in terms of mergers and acquisitions since five years prior (*M&A in Russia 2013, 2014*). In late 2014 and early 2015, the nation was going through a deep financial crisis due to currency devaluation and the situation in Crimea. This difference in circumstance explains the seemingly purposeful sharpness of the 2013 rise in inflows and outflows versus a shallow steady decrease in 2014-2015.

Figure 7

Brookings data gathered from International Monetary Fund Balance of Payments Statistics

Note. From “Russia's external position: Does financial autarky protect against sanctions?” by G.M. Milesi-Ferretti.

Figure 8

Brookings data gathered from International Monetary Fund Balance of Payments Statistics

Note. From “Russia’s external position: Does financial autarky protect against sanctions?” by G.M. Milesi-Ferretti.

Currency Value

Expanding on the analysis of Russian foreign economic relations is the negative outlook for their currency. In March after the initial entrance into Ukrainian borders and subsequent sanctions, the Ruble took a dive from 0.013 USD to 0.007 USD and then a subsequent spike to 0.018 USD in June and July. Since then, the currency has trended downwards to around 0.013 USD as recently as late March 2023; this value is within the price range of a couple of years prior to the war. Though the currency has been damaged, its backing remains strong.

Figure 9

Brookings data gathered from IMF, International Reserves and Foreign Currency Liquidity

Note. From “Russia’s external position: Does financial autarky protect against sanctions?” by G.M. Milesi-Ferretti.

The nation’s foreign exchange reserves see exposure to steadily valued assets and diversified deposits as well as an enormous securities position that accounts for almost half the Bank of Russia’s position (Milesi-Ferretti, 2022). Furthermore, as of June 2021, the order of magnitude for currency holdings was the Euro followed by Gold, and then the USD as the top three reserves. While the holding in Gold is substantial, the Bank of Russia is exposed mainly to Western currency value. This play mitigates the effect of Western sanctions on the Russian central bank while also exposing the nation to the inflationary recessive leanings of the United States as of 2022 and early 2023 (Milesi-Ferretti, 2022).

Figure 10

Brookings data gathered from the Central Bank of Russia

Note. From “Russia's external position: Does financial autarky protect against sanctions?” by G.M. Milesi-Ferretti.

Overall, the Russian currency is dependent on further participation of the Russian financial sector in world markets and the influx of international financing. The Russian central bank, along with others, has rooted itself in markets across the world. Unfortunately for the nation, these ties are being largely cut through forced sales and repurchasing of assets that result in untimely liquidation and inward financial flow.

Internal Economic Climate

Brookings described the current Russian economic position as “autarky,” but the possibility of internal success is also dire. January 2023 saw spending within the Russian budget increase 58% to result in a mind-boggling 1.8 trillion ruble budget deficit, the highest in the nation’s history (Prokopenko, 2023). The economy looks like it might collapse at times and the restrictive state of its internal capitalist system does not help to combat the situation. Ranked 125 on the 2023 Index of Economic Freedom by the Heritage Foundation, the Russian Federation is in a tough spot internally. The nation heavily restricts monetary and business freedom as well as property rights though

allowing for a solid level of trade freedom (*Russia*, 2023). This dampened capitalist economic system sits side by side with an international trade policy that heavily relies on unrestricted globalization. Thus, the expectation is that the resulting consequences of the Ukraine invasion lead to economic collapse. However, the nation has remained strong, with GDP dropping only half the expected amount in 2022 (Prokopenko, 2022).

Figure 11

Macrotrends.net data gathered from the World Bank

Note. From “*Russia GDP 1988-2023*” by macrotrends.net.

Overall, the country has had a rocky history of GDP measures since it moved away from the Soviet-planned economy. Before the war in Ukraine, the nation was expected to have a couple of percentage points of GDP growth, though now the country must save itself from collapse. The nation was prepared for this situation; according to the Carnegie Endowment, the larger companies and banks performed tests to assess hypothetical detachment from SWIFT and the cancellation of certain foreign imports. However, these tests and the relatively optimistic GDP fall do not show the full picture of certain Western imports such as microchips which will have a huge effect not seen for a while (Prokopenko, 2022). Furthermore, much of the subsistence for the manufacturing industry which is so important in Russia is their military spending that thus requires more and more military

equipment and costs will be driven upwards (Luzin, 2022). Military efforts have increased to the point where conscription is resulting in massive labor shortages for which an ending is unclear (The Moscow Times, 2022). This furthers Russia's incredibly dire demographic problem which includes low birthrates and rising migration from the country. Measures have been taken to prevent the effects of this change, however, the demographic trends are emphasized by the conscription of soldiers and increasing disapproval of the invasion within the Russian population (Kolesnikov, 2023).

Figure 12

Worlddata.info data in linear format on the population of Russia dating back to 1960

Population development in Russia since 1960

(Data in millions of inhabitants)

Note. From “Population growth in Russia” by worlddata.info.

The population of the nation is in decline and effects will show themselves within the important internal sectors such as agriculture, forestry, fishing, and manufacturing. Internal economics can be sustained through the vast natural resources in the nation but social changes such as migration, or inverted demographic trends likely restrict this possibility.

Theoretical Frameworks

An Accounting Perspective

The Russian Federation has considered its global position with regard to NATO and Western adversaries instead of fully understanding the state of its finances. From an assets versus liabilities perspective, it can be seen that what Russia traditionally provides to the world greatly outweighs its international exposure, however, what remains to be seen is a different picture.

Europe and much of the world rely on their energy and many other nations look to them for machinery and manufacturing. However, sanctions, bans, tariffs, and a climate change crisis have at least forced Western states to consider a world without Russian imports. Assuming the world finds ways to live without Russian energy or machinery, what defines the nation's place in the global market seems to fade away. There is no denying that Russia has enough natural energy sources to survive indefinitely but these sources become useless when internal necessities are the only source of demand. Similarly, the nation leverages its natural resources, including other assets in addition to energy such as timber, to force itself into an important global position, and an absence of demand disarms almost all Russian foreign policy. The nation's efforts to shift its energy trading partners to nations like India are temporary solutions that will most likely fall apart when Indian demand slows and cannot sustain the nation's desired export levels. In this way, the natural resources asset has depreciated in value.

Fortunately for the nation, their banking and financial diversification are safe and well disseminated across markets. They own important assets throughout Europe and maintain a strong influence in the economic development initiatives in important future economies. When looking at global finance and banking, western sanctions and bans matter less. Russia has strong alliances with China and an important position in BRICS which do not ease the pain of trade losses but do maintain Russian stances. The nation is ranked highly in voting power within the World Bank and has worked to become a large contributor to developing economies. The foreign assets and reserves

of the Central Bank of Russia link them strongly to the trends of Western markets; one example being the heavy investment into US equities by the funds of large banks like SberBank. This parasitic relationship that Russian investment has created makes one realize that a good Western attack against Russian banking is one first against Western markets themselves. Furthermore, efforts to attack Russian finance have proved largely ineffective. Not only did the largest banks and companies prepare for it, but the value of the Ruble actually rocketed to a 52-week high following its hammering after the initial invasion of Ukraine. Generally, Russian banking will stay a strong asset for the nation in combating decline within the global conversation.

The nation's largest liability is arguably the war in Ukraine. While military mobilization has reinvigorated the manufacturing industry, it has taken from that industry's labor force along with every other sector. The war is costing people, time, and money and has largely had little end product. Much of the Russian military force has been decimated for a purpose that is protested more and more in Russian society. A future without Russian invasion and subsequent NATO expansion into Ukraine is an unclear picture for Russia. Although it can be argued that the demographic and economic cost of preventing Western expansion outweighs the benefit of having to work harder to pursue foreign policy ideals through diplomacy. Furthermore, as the war continues, more and more nations will condemn it until allies abandon Russia because of natural fears about sovereignty. In this way, the Ukraine War is a growing liability.

From an accounting perspective, the Russian Balance sheet is quickly changing. On the asset side are depreciating resources and a steady financial position, and on the liabilities side is a rapidly toxic venture which seems to destroy a lot of national assets. While this point has not been reached yet, there will be a breakpoint where the two trends pass each other and the nation becomes heavily exposed.

The Ukrainian Quagmire, Crimea as a Theoretical Framework

On February 24th, 2022 the Russian military advanced from their positions along the Russian and Belarussian borders with Ukraine, into the country. The Russian invasion of Ukraine took shape in a multi-pronged offensive, with a spearhead of Russian helicopters and elite airborne infantry divisions descending on the Ukrainian capital of Kyiv (Burns, 2022). Russian military units had been gathering along the border with Ukraine for months, as Western military analysts and intelligence services warned the Ukrainian government that Russia was preparing large-scale maneuvers against the nation. While many in the American and European intelligence community predicted that Ukraine would be able to withhold the advance for a few weeks, the Ukrainian defenders managed to stall Russian attacks across the frontline for months (Merchant, 2022). As the Russian offensive dragged on into the summer and fall, prolonged by fierce Ukrainian resistance, the Russian military ordered a tactical withdrawal from occupied Ukrainian territory around Kyiv, and in northern and eastern parts of the nation (The Visual Journalism Team, 2023). In September and November of 2022, the Ukrainian military successfully launched counter-offensives in the occupied regions surrounding the cities of Kherson and Kharkiv, setting in place an effective stalemate that has continued to hold up into April of 2023 (FT Visual & Data Journalism team, 2023).

The immediate international response to the Russian invasion of Ukraine largely fell around pre-existing global geopolitical and ideological lines. While many Western nations were quick to denounce Russia's military intervention, nations such as Iran and South Africa have repeatedly voiced their support for Russia's military ambitions, and have rejected Western calls to impose sanctions on Russia (*World Reaction to the Invasion of Ukraine*, 2023). The Russian Federation has found a select few on the international stage willing to stand by them as they wage war in Europe, but have largely found themselves at odds with the international community, especially with those

nations that are a part of NATO, the European Union, and nations guaranteed under American military protection.

An important map for current conditions and a strong parallel is the 2014 situation in Crimea. The Western response to the illegal Russian annexation of the Crimean Peninsula in February of 2014 has largely been regarded as a failure by political and historical analysts. The sanctions imposed by the United States, Canada, and the European Union were aimed at inflicting enough serious damage on the Russian economy to deter them from pursuing any other aggressive actions against Ukraine (Aslund, 2020). The sanctions imposed on the Russian government and on individual Russian citizens involved in the annexation did succeed at causing the Russian economy to enter into a decline in the first quarter of 2015 (Russian GDP shrank by 2.2%), but failed at dissuading Russia from engaging in further military aggression. (Aslund, 2020; Christie, 2015).

Some Western policy analysts have suggested that the sanctions imposed on Russia conveniently aligned with certain economic trends that worsened the financial fallout on the Russian economy. Chief among these trends was the collapse of global oil prices shortly following the annexation of Crimea, which badly damaged the Russian economy (Ashford, 2016). Despite this potential contributing factor, Western sanctions had a tremendous effect on Russian economic health and stability. Sanctions had a noticeable impact on the size of Russian foreign debt, forcing a decline from USD 732 billion in July 2014 to USD 482 billion in June 2019. Russian corporations no longer had refinancing options available, having most avenues to restructure debt closed by American and European sanctions. According to one estimation, this may have caused Russian entities to forgo investments worth up to 32 percent of Russian GDP in the following five years (Aslund, 2020). Figure 7 further illustrates the disastrous consequences of Western sanctions, which caused a nearly 35 percent decline in Russian financial inflows. Furthermore, the value of the Russian Ruble fell nearly 76 percent from the imposition of the original sanctions to January 2016 (Ashford, 2016).

Clearly, sanctions had a negative effect on the Russian economy. In the immediate aftermath of their implementation, this point is indisputable. Yet in the economic and political long-run, they have not been regarded as favorably. The Russian economy, while permanently damaged by the sanctions, did not collapse. More so, the sanctions also did not succeed in preventing a military escalation in the region. In August 2014, only six months after the Crimean annexation, troops from the Russian military entered the eastern Ukrainian regions of Luhansk and Donetsk to supplement local rebel forces. This action was subsequently met with additional sanctions from the United States and the European Union (Zinets & Madorsky, 2014). With the original aim of the Western nations considered, sanctions failed to prevent an escalation of military conflict in Ukraine (Wroughton, 2014).

The West, momentarily, won the economic war that resulted from Russia's Crimean expansion. In the physical realm, Russia triumphed. There was no hope of actual Western military intervention led by NATO into Ukraine as a result of Russia's annexation. Russia had not violated the territorial integrity of any NATO member and could act without the threat of a joint American-European response (Volker, 2014). It is likely that Russia operated under the same assumption that the West would fail to significantly affect its military campaign in Ukraine when it launched its invasion of the country in February of 2022. This assumption has effectively destroyed the Russian economy and military and has isolated the country on a global scale to a near-unprecedented degree.

It is clear to see why Russia may have operated under the assumption that the West would fail to defend Ukraine economically and in a military, and physical sense. The immediate Western response to the Russian invasion was to sanction large sectors of the Russian economy, individual Russian oligarchs, and freeze foreign assets and holdings of the Russian government and some private businesses (Cizek, 2014). The response from NATO and other American allies was nearly identical to 2014: denounce the invasion and sanction the economy. However, the West has evolved

its approach to dealing with breaches of sovereignty, especially in Europe. The United States, aided by rhetoric and requests from many Eastern European countries, has revolutionized the approach of liberal nations to the provision of aid. As of January 2023, the United States alone has sent over USD \$76 billion to Ukraine in assistance. 31 percent of that assistance came in the form of direct military aid from American weapons stockpiles, and a further 30 percent constituted further military aid (Masters & Merrow, 2023).

The West has been sure to prioritize the literal, physical war in Ukraine, and has rather allowed the economic war to go unresolved. The Russian economy certainly is not in a healthy spot relative to its position before the commencement of the war in 2022. However, the predicted collapse of the Russian economy has not materialized. The Biden Administration projected that the sanctions it had implemented against the would cause a 15 percent reduction in Russian GDP in 2022, with President Biden publically exclaiming that the Russian economy would be “reduced to rubble.” In reality, the Russian economy only contracted by 2.2 percent in 2022, and was projected to grow by 0.3 percent in 2023, outpacing the growth of some European countries (Hussein, 2023).

The damages on the economic front pale in comparison to the disastrous military damages that Russia has incurred fighting in Ukraine. Russia has resulted in sending forced constricts and prisoners to the frontline as nearly 200,000 soldiers have died fighting in Ukraine (Gibbons-Neff & Schmitt & Cooper. 2023). Nothing could have prepared Russia for the sheer amount of assistance that Western nations were prepared to give to Ukraine to protect liberal democracy against authoritarian domination. The colossal military failure of the Russian army is second only to the incredibly rhetorical embarrassment that Russia has brought upon itself. Ukraine’s own allies were convinced of the fact that in a matter of weeks, Russia would resorb its southern neighbor, and yet nothing could be further from the truth. The Western intelligence assertion that Russia would easily topple the Ukrainian state is perhaps less of an insult to Ukraine than it is such a gross misunderstanding of Russian military competence.

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